

A Gaussian-based adaptive sliding mode control scheme for wireless power transfer systems

Xudong Gao^a, Wenjie Cao^a, Qiang Yang^a, Sang-Woon Jeon^b and Jun Zhang^a

^aSchool of Artificial Intelligence/School of Future Technology, Nanjing University of Information Science and Technology, Nanjing, China; ^bDepartment of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Hanyang University, Ansan, Korea

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, many intelligent control schemes have been adopted in wireless power transfer systems. The control strategy affects the time-domain performance of the system. The recent studies are mostly focus on global control strategies, which involve using the same set of controller parameters during system operation. However, the global control strategy cannot adaptively adjust the controller parameters based on the system state, so the system cannot make the optimal response. To compensate for the shortcomings of the global control strategy, in this paper, a Gaussian-based adaptive sliding mode control scheme for wireless power transfer systems is proposed. Firstly, Gaussian function is applied to traditional pulse width modulation based sliding mode control as an adaptive technique, forcing controller parameters to vary dynamically with the tendency of function, which improves the wireless power transfer system performance. Then, the optimal controller parameters are obtained by using modified particle swarm optimization, and the system performance is further improved. Finally, the effectiveness of the proposed scheme is verified by simulation. The wireless power transfer system performs well even if there are uncertainties.

KEYWORDS

Adaptive sliding mode control; Gaussian adaptive technique; modified particle swarm optimization; wireless power transfer system

1. Introduction

In recent years, the wireless power transfer (WPT) technology is widely used in the field of biomedical (Basar et al., 2018; Pal and Ki, 2020), consumer electronics (Lillholm et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022), unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) (Wu et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2021a), and so forth. However, there are still many technical challenges to realize leapfrog development of the WPT technology, such as energy efficiency (Khan et al., 2018; Shu et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2023), omnidirectional charging (Feng et al., 2022; Han et al., 2019; Zhang and Zhang, 2020), control strategy (Li et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2020), and so on. The control strategy affects the time-domain performance of the system.

In order to improve control performance, researchers have invested a lot of effort and proposed many remarkable works, which are mainly divided into three categories: global control strategy, multistage control strategy, and adaptive control strategy.

The system uses the same set of controller parameters during operation, when the global control strategy is applied. In (Yang et al., 2019), Yang *et al.* proposed a multi-objective H-infinity control design method based on genetic algorithm (GA), which balances the time domain and robust performance of wireless power transfer systems. In (Liu et al., 2022), Liu *et al.* proposed a resource aware distributed differential evolution strategy for designing controllers in power electronic circuits, which can obtain optimal solutions in a short time.

Although the global control strategy has improved system performance to some extent, it ignores the relationship between the indicators evaluating system performance and the time axis. In (Gao et al., 2022), Gao *et al.* proposed a three-stage control system design strategy for nonlinear wireless power transfer system. Firstly, according to the characteristics of the system in different stages, the simulation process is divided into three stages, which are defined as: start-up stage, tracking stage and steady state stage. Then, the fitness function is set according to the optimization problem of each stage. Next, genetic algorithm is used to solve the optimization problem, and the optimal controller parameters of each stage are obtained. Compared with the global control scheme, this scheme makes the system perform better.

The three-stage control strategy has some improvement, but it divides each stage roughly. So, there is still space for further optimization. The adaptive control scheme is an improvement on the three-stage control scheme. Theoretically, it can be seen as the scheme solving the optimal controller parameter set at each point in time. In (Puchta et al., 2020), Puchta *et al.* proposed a Gaussian adaptive proportion integration differentiation (GAPID) controller, which uses Gaussian function to adaptively adjust the gain of the traditional proportion integration differentiation (PID) controller, and the overall performance of the system has been greatly improved.

The adaptive control strategy can improve the system performance, but its disadvantage is that there are many controller parameters, and the selection of optimal parameters is the key. Evolutionary algorithm (EA) is not a specific algorithm, but a cluster of algorithms that have the characteristics of self-organization, adaptation, and self-learning. It can effectively handle complex problems that traditional optimization algorithms cannot solve without being limited by the nature of the problem. Particle swarm optimization (PSO) is a evolutionary computation technology with strong global search ability, and has been proved to be an effective method in controller parameter design by many researchers. Upadhyay *et al.* (Upadhyay et al., 2022) used PSO to optimize the gains K_p and K_i of proportion integration (PI) controller and successfully maintains the DC link voltage at half of the DC source voltage on the input side. Wang *et al.* (Wang et al., 2022) used PSO to adjust the weighting factors of model predictive control (MPC), which reduced the switching loss of permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) system and achieved good current control.

In this paper, a Gaussian-based adaptive SMC (GASMC) scheme for WPT systems is proposed. The control method applies Gaussian function to traditional PWM-based SM controller. To the best of our knowledge, the Gaussian-based adaptive SMC scheme is first proposed and applied to WPT systems. After the application of Gaussian adaptive technique, parameters of the proposed control scheme also increase. In addition, the curve of the influence of parameters on system performance is not monotonous, and the parameters are interrelated. All these make it difficult to find the optimal controller parameters. In order to improve the WPT system performance, modified particle swarm optimization (MPSO) is used as optimization tool to find the optimal controller parameters. The balance was found among the three indicators evaluating the WPT system performance (tracking time, steady-state error and maximum rip-

ple voltage) by using the controller with the optimal parameters, the WPT system achieves good performance.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows.

- (1) An adaptive sliding mode control scheme for wireless power transfer system is proposed. The controller parameters can be adjusted adaptively according to the system state, and the system performance is improved.
- (2) The improved PSO algorithm is used to search the optimal control model, which improves the controller performance.
- (3) When the load or mutual inductance changes, the proposed scheme can still maintain good performance of the wireless power transfer system.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Wireless power transfer system

The diagram of the WPT system is shown in Fig. 1. The system consists of three parts: coupling system, rectifier and buck converter. The coupling system realizes contactless transmission of energy, the rectifier realizes conversion from AC signal to DC signal, and the buck converter realizes output voltage management.

The mathematical model P of the WPT system is as follows:

$$V_{out} = M_2 e^{X_1 t} + N_2 e^{Y_1 t} + D_1 V_{in}. \quad (1)$$

The derivation process of (1) and parameter settings of the WPT system have been described in (Gao and Deng, 2018).

Figure 1. The diagram of the WPT system.

2.2. PWM-based sliding mode control

For a control system

$$\dot{x} = f(x, u, t) \quad (2)$$

the basic sliding mode control needs to determine the switching function s and control function u , as shown in (3) and (4).

$$s(x) = s(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n) \quad (3)$$

$$u = \begin{cases} u^+(x), & s(x) > 0 \\ u^-(x), & s(x) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $u^+(x) \neq u^-(x)$.

To ensure the existence of sliding mode, (5) must be satisfied.

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} s \dot{s} < 0 \quad (5)$$

As shown in Fig. 2, different from the basic sliding mode control, PWM-based SMC generates switching signal u by comparing control signal v_c and ramp signal v_r , forcing the state variable to move towards the sliding surface. In one cycle, electronic switch has two states: on and off, corresponding to the switching signals $u = 1$ and $u = 0$. When the system state is at point A, the switching signal $u = 0$ and the switching function $s(x)$ moves from negative to positive. When the system state is at point B, the switching signal $u = 1$ and the switching function $s(x)$ moves from positive to negative.

Figure 2. Principle of PWM-based SMC.

2.3. Particle swarm optimization

The pseudocode of PSO is shown in Algorithm 1. PSO finds the global optimal solution through the interaction between particles. In the initialization, the position $X_i = [x_{i1} \ x_{i2} \ \dots \ x_{iD}]$ and velocity $V_i = [v_{i1} \ v_{i2} \ \dots \ v_{iD}]$ of N particles are randomly generated in the solution space, where $1 < i < N$ represents the individual index and D represents the problem dimension. Each dimension x_{id} of position has a certain search range $[x_{lower,d} \ x_{upper,d}]$, and each dimension v_{id} of velocity has a certain search range $[v_{lower,d} \ v_{upper,d}]$.

In every generation, it is necessary to find the individual extreme value $pbest_i$ of each particle X_i by

$$pbest_i = \begin{cases} fit(X_i), & \text{if } fit(X_i) < pbest_i \\ pbest_i, & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where fit is fitness function.

Next, the global extreme value $gbest$ is needed to find by

$$gbest = \begin{cases} \min(pbest), & \text{if } \min(pbest) < gbest \\ gbest, & \text{Otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Then, the position and velocity of each dimension are updated by

$$v_{id} = \omega v_{id} + C_1 \text{random}(0,1)(pbest_{id} - x_{id}) + C_2 \text{random}(0,1)(gbest_d - x_{id}) \quad (8)$$

$$x_{id} = x_{id} + v_{id} \quad (9)$$

where ω is the inertia factor, representing the tendency of particle to maintain its previous velocity, C_1 is the self-learning factor, representing the tendency of particle to approach its historical best position, and C_2 is the group-learning factor, which represents the tendency of particles to approach the global best position. Note that if the value of a dimension of position or velocity exceeds search range, it needs to be set to the corresponding boundary value.

The above operations are performed for each iteration until the terminal condition is met.

Algorithm 1 PSO to search global optimal solution

Input: Population size, Maximum iterations, Dimension size, Inertia factor, Self-learning factor, Group-learning factor

Output: Global optimal solution

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1: function PSO
2:   Initialize each particle randomly
3:   for 1:1:Maximum iterations do
4:     Evaluate the fitness of each particle
5:     Update the historical best position of each particle
6:     Update the global best position of the population
7:     Update the velocity and position of each particle
8:   end for
9:   return Global optimal solution
10: end function

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3. Main results

The proposed Gaussian-based adaptive SMC scheme is shown in Fig. 3. The part surrounded by the dotted red line is the schematic diagram of the WPT system. The part surrounded by the dotted blue line is the Gaussian-based adaptive SMC scheme proposed in this paper. The scheme consists of three key modules: parameter update algorithm, Gaussian function and PWM-based SM controller for the WPT system, in which the parameter update algorithm decides whether to update the input of the Gaussian function at the next moment according to the existence condition. Its detailed description is shown in Fig. 9. PWM-based SM controller for the WPT system and Gaussian function are described in detailed in Section 3.1 and Section 3.2, respectively.

Figure 3. The schematic diagram of proposed Gaussian-based adaptive SMC scheme for the WPT system.

The Gaussian-based adaptive SMC scheme applies specific adaptive rules, Gaussian function, to traditional PWM-based SM controller, the controller parameters can be dynamically adjusted according to the Gaussian function to make the WPT system achieving good performance. The execution process of the proposed Gaussian-based adaptive SMC scheme for the WPT system is as follows.

- (1) Step 1: The parameter update algorithm and the PWM-based SM controller for the WPT system receive data from the WPT system.
- (2) Step 2: Parameter update algorithm predicts n control signals v_c and takes the mean value of it.
- (3) Step 3: Compare the mean value calculated in Step 2 with the ramp signal v_r . If the existence condition as shown in (12) is met, the output of the parameter update algorithm, δ , is updated; otherwise, δ remains the value at the last time.
- (4) Step 4: δ obtained in Step 3 is used as the input of the Gaussian function, which produces the controller parameter c_2 at the next moment.
- (5) Step 5: The comparator outputs gate pulse u to control the action of the switch S .

3.1. Design of PWM-based SM controller for the WPT system

The PWM-based SM controller design for the WPT system is as follows.

Select the switching function and control function as

$$s = \lambda_1(V_{ref} - V_{out}) + \lambda_2 \frac{d(V_{ref} - V_{out})}{dt} + \lambda_3 \int (V_{ref} - V_{out}) dt \quad (10)$$

$$u = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{when } s > 0 \\ 0, & \text{when } s < 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where λ_1 , λ_2 , and λ_3 are sliding coefficients.

The existence condition is derived by using (5) and (10).

$$0 < -L_s \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2} - \frac{1}{R_{out}C_s} \right) i_{C_s} + L_s C_s \frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_2} (V_{ref} - V_{out}) + V_{out} < V_{in} = \frac{\pi \omega^3 M_{12} M_{23} M_{34} R_L V_1}{4(\omega^4 M_{12}^2 M_{34}^2 + Z_1 Z_2 Z_3 Z_4 + \omega^2 k)} \quad (12)$$

Deriving the equivalent control law u_{eq} and mapping it to duty cycle. $\dot{s} = 0$ yields the equivalent control law.

$$0 < u_{eq} = -\frac{L_s}{V_{in}} \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2} - \frac{1}{R_{out}C_s} \right) i_{C_s} + \frac{\lambda_3 L_s C_s}{\lambda_2 V_{in}} (V_{ref} - V_{out}) + \frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}} < 1 \quad (13)$$

Inequality (13) multiply by V_{in} gives

$$0 < \bar{u}_{eq} = -L_s \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2} - \frac{1}{R_{out}C_s} \right) i_{C_s} + L_s C_s \frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_2} (V_{ref} - V_{out}) + V_{out} < V_{in}. \quad (14)$$

The equivalent control function (14) is converted into duty cycle D_1 , and $0 < D_1 = v_c/v_r < 1$. The equivalent control signal v_c and ramp signal v_r are as follows.

$$0 < v_c = \bar{u}_{eq} = -K_1 i_{C_s} + K_2 (V_{ref} - V_{out}) + V_{out} < V_{in} = \frac{\pi \omega^3 M_{12} M_{23} M_{34} R_L V_1}{4(\omega^4 M_{12}^2 M_{34}^2 + Z_1 Z_2 Z_3 Z_4 + \omega^2 k)} \quad (15)$$

$$v_r = V_{in} = \frac{\pi \omega^3 M_{12} M_{23} M_{34} R_L V_1}{4(\omega^4 M_{12}^2 M_{34}^2 + Z_1 Z_2 Z_3 Z_4 + \omega^2 k)} \quad (16)$$

where $K_1 = L(c_1 - \frac{1}{R_{out}C_s})$, $K_2 = c_2 L_s C_s$, $c_1 = \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2}$, $c_2 = \frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_2}$.

3.2. Gaussian function design

The Gaussian adaptive function proposed in this paper is described as

$$f(\delta) = k_1 - (k_1 - k_0)e^{-\frac{\delta^2}{2c^2}} \quad (17)$$

where δ is the input of the Gaussian function, k_1 is the boundary limit when the input approaches ∞ , k_0 is the boundary limit when the input approaches 0, k_1 and k_0 together determine the opening direction of the function, and c determines the concavity of curve.

This function has the following characteristics: function and its derivative are smooth, there is upper and lower bounds, the concavity is adjustable. The above features make it suitable as an adaptive technology to improve the performance of traditional controllers. The function and its derivative are smooth, so the parameters of the controller don't abruptly change and the response of the system is smooth. The function is bounded, which denotes that the variation range of controller parameters are limited and the behavior of the system is controllable. The adjustable concavity means that the rate of change of controller parameters can be adjusted.

Figure 4. The impact of parameters k_1 and k_0 on open direction of Gaussian function.

Figure 5. Impact of parameter variation on the shape of Gaussian function.

The influence of parameters k_1 and k_0 on the opening direction of the function is shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 4a is the case where k_1 is less than k_0 , the Gaussian function is convex; Fig. 4b is the case where k_1 is greater than k_0 , the Gaussian function is concave.

The impact of parameter variation on the shape of Gaussian curve is shown in Fig. 5 (taking k_1 less than k_0 as an example), and parameter settings are listed in Table 1.

Theoretically, there are six parameters need to be optimized after applying Gaussian function to controller parameters c_1 and c_2 . In fact, only four parameters need to be optimized. In the WPT system, the influence of controller parameter c_1 on the system performance is much less than that of c_2 . After weighting the impact of c_1 on the WPT system performance and computational time, the Gaussian function is applied only to controller parameter c_2 . In this way, traditional PWM-based SM controller has two parameters (c_1, c_2), and the Gaussian-based adaptive SM controller has four parameters (c_1, k_1, k_0, c).

Table 1. The specification of parameter settings of Gaussian function when testing parameter effect

Parameter	Basic value	Variation range
k_1	3	± 2
k_0	10	± 2
c	3	± 2

3.3. Fitness function design

In order to find the optimal controller parameters, it is necessary to design a cost function as the optimization objective, each item of the cost function corresponds to an indicator evaluating the performance of the WPT system. The purpose of the cost function is to make trade-offs between these indicators.

The optimization objectives are mainly to reduce the tracking time, steady-state error, and the maximum ripple voltage, which can be formulated as

$$\max F = K_1 e^{-f_1/K_2} + K_3 e^{-f_2/K_4} + K_5 e^{-f_3/K_6} \quad (18)$$

where K_i , $\{i \mid i = 1, 3, 5\}$, is the reward factor, representing the contribution of the j_{th} , $\{j \mid j = 1, 2, 3\}$, indicator f_j to the fitness function. K_i , $\{i \mid i = 2, 4, 6\}$, is the decay rate of the j_{th} indicator f_j . By adjusting the decay rate, the exploration and exploitation capabilities of the MPSO algorithm can be effectively balanced, thereby finding the optimal solution.

The specification of the constant parameters in the fitness function is shown in Table 2.

Indicator f_1 measures the tracking time and is defined as

$$f_1 = t_1 - t_0 \quad (19)$$

where t_1 is the settling time of output voltage and t_0 is the start time.

Indicator f_2 measures the steady-state error and is defined as

$$f_2 = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} |V_{out} - V_{ref}| dt \quad (20)$$

where t_2 is the end time of simulation, V_{out} is the output voltage (load voltage) and V_{ref} is the reference voltage.

Indicator f_3 measures the maximum ripple voltage and is defined as

$$f_3 = V_{pp} \quad (21)$$

where V_{pp} is the peak-to-peak value of the output voltage.

Table 2. The specification of constant parameters in the fitness function

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit
Start time	t_0	0	s
Stop time	t_2	0.1	s
Reference voltage	V_{ref}	2.5	V
Reward factor of f_1	K_1	20	x
Decay rate of f_1	K_2	11	x
Reward factor of f_2	K_3	20	x
Decay rate of f_2	K_4	13	x
Reward factor of f_3	K_5	20	x
Decay rate of f_3	K_6	11	x

3.4. Analysis of the influence of controller parameters on the WPT system performance

Due to the large number of controller parameters and indicators evaluating system performance, in this part, the effects of controller parameters on system performance are analyzed only by taking the impacts of k_0 and k_1 on output voltage settling time and maximum ripple voltage as an example. Fig. 6 shows the influence of controller parameter k_0 on output voltage settling time indicator f_1 and maximum ripple voltage indicator f_3 . As can be seen from the figure, with the increase of k_0 , indicator f_1 shows an upward trend, which means that the settling time increases and the system tracking performance gets worse. On the contrary, with the increase of k_0 , indicator f_3 shows a downward trend, which means the maximum ripple voltage reduces, the system performance improves. Fig. 7 shows the influence of parameter k_1 on indicators f_1 and f_3 , and both indicators show a trend of fluctuation.

Figure 6. The effect of controller parameter k_0 on indicators f_1 and f_3 .

Through the analysis of these two figures, it can be concluded that the controller

parameters are mutually affected, and the curve of the effect of controller parameters on system performance is non-monotonic, which increases the difficulty of controller parameter design.

Figure 7. The effect of controller parameter k_1 on indicators f_1 and f_3 .

3.5. Searching for optimal parameters

The process of searching for optimal parameters of the Gaussian-based adaptive SM controller by using MPSO is as follows.

- (1) Step 1: Randomly initialize the position $X = [X_1 X_2 \dots X_N]$ and velocity $V = [V_1 V_2 \dots V_N]$ of each particle by

$$x_{id} = x_{lower,d} + (x_{upper,d} - x_{lower,d}) \times random(0, 1) \quad (22)$$

$$v_{id} = v_{lower,d} + (v_{upper,d} - v_{lower,d}) \times random(0, 1) \quad (23)$$

where each particle X_i represents a set of controller parameters, and each dimension d corresponds to one controller parameters.

- (2) Step 2: Calculate the fitness value by

$$fitness = F \quad (24)$$

where F is the cost function.

- (3) Step 3: Update individual extreme value for each particle by using (6).
- (4) Step 4: Update global extreme value by using (7).
- (5) Step 5: Update velocity and position by using (8) and (9).
- (6) Step 6: Determine whether the terminal condition is met. If so, output the optimal solution, that is, the optimal controller parameters, otherwise back to the Step 2.

The pseudocode of MPSO is shown in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 MPSO to search optimal controller parameters

Input: Controller parameters c, k_1, k_0 , and c_1 **Output:** Optimal controller parameters

```
1: function MPSO( $c, k_1, k_0, c_1$ )
2:    $N \leftarrow 30$  // Population size
3:    $G \leftarrow 1000$  // Number of iterations
4:    $\omega \leftarrow 0.8$  // Inertia factor
5:    $C_1 \leftarrow 0.5$  // Self-learning factor
6:    $C_2 \leftarrow 0.5$  // Group-learning factor
7:   for  $ii = 1 \rightarrow G$  do
8:      $fitness \leftarrow \text{FIT}(X)$  //  $\text{FIT}(X) = 1/F$ ,  $X = [X_1 X_2 \dots X_N]$ 
9:     for  $jj = 1 \rightarrow N$  do // Update individual extreme value
10:      if  $pbest[jj] < fitness[jj]$  then
11:         $pbest[jj] \leftarrow fitness[jj]$ 
12:      end if
13:    end for
14:    if  $gbest < \max(pbest)$  then // Update global extreme value
15:       $[gbest \ pbest\_index] \leftarrow \max(pbest)$ 
16:       $parameters \leftarrow X[pbest\_index]$ 
17:    end if
18:     $V = \omega V + C_1 \text{RAND}(0, 1)(pbest - X) + C_2 \text{RAND}(0, 1)(\text{REPMAT}(gbest, N, 1) - X)$  // Update velocity, where  $V = [V_1 V_2 \dots V_N]$  and "REPMAT" expands gbest to an N-by-1 matrix
19:    for  $jj = 1 \rightarrow d$  do // Boundary velocity processing
20:      if  $V_d > v_{upper,d}$  then
21:         $V_d \leftarrow v_{upper,d}$ 
22:      end if
23:      if  $V_d < v_{lower,d}$  then
24:         $V_d \leftarrow v_{lower,d}$ 
25:      end if
26:    end for
27:     $X = X + V$  // Update position
28:    for  $jj = 1 \rightarrow d$  do // Boundary position processing
29:      if  $X_d > x_{upper,d}$  then
30:         $X_d \leftarrow x_{upper,d}$ 
31:      end if
32:      if  $X_d < x_{lower,d}$  then
33:         $X_d \leftarrow x_{lower,d}$ 
34:      end if
35:    end for
36:  end for
37:  return optimal controller parameters
38: end function
```

4. Simulation

To verify that the proposed control scheme can make the WPT system achieving good performance, Matlab/Simulink is used as the simulation platform, as shown in

Fig. 8. The simulation circuit consists of four parts: coupling system, rectifier, buck converter and Gaussian-based adaptive SMC scheme. The first three parts constitute the open-loop WPT system. The "Stop Time" and "Sampling Time" in the simulation environment are set as 0.1 seconds and $3e^{-8}$ seconds, respectively. Fig. 9 shows the full schematic diagram of Gaussian-based adaptive SMC scheme for the WPT system.

Figure 8. Simulation diagram of the WPT system with Gaussian-based adaptive SMC scheme.

Figure 9. The full schematic diagram of Gaussian-based adaptive SMC scheme for the WPT system.

4.1. Comparisons and simulation results

In order to verify the superiority of the proposed scheme, three advanced control methods are used as comparison controllers in this section: the DDPG controller proposed

in Zhang et al. (2021b)., the GAPID controller proposed in Puchta et al. (2020)., and the segmented controller proposed in Gao et al. (2022). The optimization results are shown in Fig. 11-Fig. 13 and Table 3. Fig. 10a is the control signal v_c , ramp signal v_r curve, Fig. 10b is the switch state curve.

Table 3. Performance comparison of different controllers

Controller	Settling Time	Steady State Error	Maximum Ripple Voltage
DDPG	194.62ms	568.06mV	5.7662mV
GAPID	2.3173ms	425.37mV	5.8585mV
Segmented	2.1879ms	36.653mV	5.2389mV
GASMC	5.1923ms	10.165mV	37.852 μ V

(a) The waveforms of control signal v_c and ramp signal v_r .

(b) The waveform of switch S .

Figure 10. The diagram of control signal, ramp signal, and switch signal.

(a) The tracking curve of output voltage of the WPT system.

(b) Output voltage curve after the WPT system reaches steady state.

Figure 11. Output voltage response of the WPT system.

Fig. 11a is the output voltage tracking curve of the WPT system, which shows the tracking time (indicator f_1 evaluating the system performance) obtained by using the different controllers. It can be observed that, except for the DDPG controller, which

has a longer output voltage settling time, the other three controllers have output voltage settling time within the same order of magnitude. Specifically, the settling time of the output voltage obtained using different controllers are shown in Table 3.

Fig. 11b shows the output voltage curve after the system reaches steady state. It can be seen from the figure that the steady-state error (indicator f_2) obtained by using the GASMC controller is significantly smaller than that obtained by using the other three comparison controller. In detail, the steady-state error values obtained using different controllers are shown in Table 3. From this table, we can further see that compared with the three comparison controllers, the proposed GASMC controller improved the steady-state error indicator by 98.21%, 97.61%, and 72.27%, respectively. This indicates that the WPT system with the proposed GASMC controller can output the desired voltage more accurately.

Additionally, the maximum ripple voltage (indicator f_3) obtained by using the proposed GASMC controller is also significantly smaller than that obtained by using the three comparison controller. From Table 3, we can detailedly understand that compared to the other three controllers, the proposed GASMC controller improves the maximum ripple voltage indicator by 99.34%, 99.35%, and 99.28%, respectively. This indicates that the WPT system with the proposed GASMC controller can output the desired voltage with less fluctuation.

4.2. Tracking performance with uncertainties

To verify the reliability of the proposed scheme in the presence of uncertainties, load R_{out} and mutual inductor M_{23} are considered as uncertainties for the subsequent simulation.

Figure 12. Tracking performance curves when output load changes.

In the simulation environment, using the proposed GASMC controller, when the load changes in the range of 69Ω to 87Ω and the mutual inductor M_{23} changes in the range of 7×10^{-6} H to 10.5×10^{-6} H, the WPT system can still maintain the good state, and the tracking performance is better than that obtained by using the other three comparison controllers. The simulation results are shown in Fig. 12-Fig. 13.

Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 show the tracking performance of the WPT system when the

load resistance R_{out} and mutual inductor M_{23} changes, respectively. From these two figures, we can see that regardless of load R_{out} or mutual inductor M_{23} variations, the proposed GASMC controller exhibits stronger anti-interference capabilities, including faster response speed and smaller fluctuation. In contrast, the DDPG controller performs the worst, especially when load R_{out} and mutual inductor M_{23} decrease, as it fails to track the reference voltage. Additionally, compared to GAPID, the segmented controller shows larger voltage fluctuation when facing interference.

(a) M_{23} suddenly changes from 7.5×10^{-6} H to 7×10^{-6} H at 0.5s. (b) M_{23} suddenly changes from 7.5×10^{-6} H to 10.5×10^{-6} H at 0.5s.

Figure 13. Tracking performance curves when mutual inductor M_{23} changes.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, an adaptive sliding mode control scheme based on Gaussian function for the wireless power transfer system is proposed. The controller parameters change with the trend of Gaussian function. In order to find the optimal Gaussian model, particle swarm optimization algorithm was selected as the optimization algorithm. The fitness function considers multiple indicators evaluating system performance, including the settling time, steady-state error and maximum ripple voltage. Moreover, the effectiveness of the proposed scheme has been verified by simulation. Compared with the other three comparison control strategy, the proposed adaptive control strategy performs better during the system operation.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported in part by the National Natural Science Foundation of China under Grant 62006124, in part by the Nature Science Foundation of Jiangsu Province under Project BK20200811, in part by the Natural Science Foundation of the Jiangsu Higher Education Institutions of China under Grant 20KJB520006, in part by the Startup Foundation for Introducing Talent of NUIST, and in part by the Graduate Research and Innovation Projects of Jiangsu Province.

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